

Title: Lucky

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

My grandmother, Nana, passed away in New York in the winter of 2020. With the coronavirus still raging, none of my extended family was able to fly east to pack up her apartment. The task, instead, fell to my girlfriend, Amanda, who was living in the city at the time. Near the end of the process, I received a voice memo from Amanda. Sitting at my grandmother's piano, she recorded one of the last scores that hadn't been boxed away: Edward MacDowell's "To a Wild Rose." For such a gentle and unassuming piece, the music carried startling gravitas. It seemed to me that the music served as the parting statement of an apartment where my grandparents had spent so much of their lives, the last expression of a place that was central to my notion of family. Amanda's recording allowed me to play and replay its "voice" as often as I needed. *Lucky* explores the ways in which "To a Wild Rose" has helped me process Nana's death—how it has served as an expression of my grief and a gateway to my memories, as well as a shaper of both. *Lucky* is dedicated to Nana.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Lucky is a 4-channel, data-driven, electroacoustic composition for the Wacom tablet and Kyma. In addition to its extra-musical program, *Lucky* explores the musical and expressive capabilities of the Wacom tablet, a repurposed instrument originally designed as a digital drawing surface for visual artists. Throughout *Lucky*, data from the Wacom tablet is mapped in Kyma in various ways, allowing the performer to both initiate and dynamically control musical events in real-time.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

Technical requirements (provided by venue):

- Two tables (or projector stands) 56 inches by 25 inches by 17 inches (HWD)

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- System will output 4 channels of audio from ¼ inch outputs
- Technical requirements (provided by performer):
- Wacom Tablet
 - Laptop with Kyma sound design software
 - Kyma's PacaMara hardware
 - Audio Interface (System will output 4 channels of audio from ¼ inch outputs)
 - All the necessary cables to connect Wacom, laptop and audio interface

Lucky is best suited for the main performance space, Tivoli Vredenburg, though it would work in the local Utrecht venues if those venues have 4-channel speaker set-ups.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Video: <https://vimeo.com/916572186>

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ETHICAL STANDARDS

This work did not involve research with people or animals.